

Supplementary for ASaiM-MT: A validated and optimized ASaiM workflow for metatranscriptomics analysis within Galaxy framework.

1	2
genus	abundance
Clostridium	76.65512
Coprothermobacter	20.75226
Thermodesulfobiaceae unclassified	2.27984
Methanothermobacter	0.26989
Escherichia	0.04289

Supplementary figure S1: MetaPhlAn2 Genus-Level Abundance: Genus-level results from MetaPhlAn2 show that the most abundant genus was *Clostridium* (76.66%), followed by *Coprothermobacter* (20.75%). Unclassified members of the Thermodesulfobiaceae family made up 2.28% of the community, followed by *Methanothermobacter* (0.27%) and *Escherichia* (0.04%).

# Gene Family	humann2_Abundance-RPKs
# Gene Family	humann2_Abundance-RPKs
UNMAPPED	109359.0000000000
UniRef50_P62593: Beta-lactamase TEM	51842.4304363200
UniRef50_P62593: Beta-lactamase TEM g_Clostridium.s_Clostridium_thermocellum	51842.4304363200
UniRef50_R5FV61	46966.2923149157
UniRef50_R5FV61 g_Clostridium.s_Clostridium_thermocellum	46966.2923149157
UniRef50_P80579: Thioredoxin	41633.7457772871
UniRef50_P80579: Thioredoxin g_Clostridium.s_Clostridium_thermocellum	41633.7457772871
UniRef50_A3DC67	35556.2380614022
UniRef50_A3DC67 g_Clostridium.s_Clostridium_thermocellum	35556.2380614022
UniRef50_Q2RHZ4: UPF0297 protein Moth_1643	24282.8291369743

Supplementary figure S2a: HUMAnN2 Gene Family Abundance: First 10 rows of the UniRef gene family abundance results from HUMAnN2. Abundance is represented as in RPK values, prior to renormalization.

# Pathway	humann2_Abundance
# Pathway	humann2_Abundance
UNMAPPED	11417.7392070186
UNINTEGRATED	65807.9719501939
UNINTEGRATED g_Clostridium.s_Clostridium_thermocellum	48238.6191078367
UNINTEGRATED g_Coprothermobacter.s_Coprothermobacter_proteolyticus	6335.2676240042
UNINTEGRATED g_Methanothermobacter.s_Methanothermobacter_thermautotrophicus	80.7884346284
PWY-6305: putrescine biosynthesis IV	764.5363426532
PWY-6305: putrescine biosynthesis IV g_Clostridium.s_Clostridium_thermocellum	751.0036125447
PWY-7219: adenosine ribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis	200.9317959763
PWY-7219: adenosine ribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis g_Clostridium.s_Clostridium_thermocellum	120.0840535241
PWY-7219: adenosine ribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis g_Coprothermobacter.s_Coprothermobacter_proteolyticus	76.5645459546

Supplementary figure S2b: HUMAnN2 Pathway Abundance: First 10 rows of the pathway abundance results from HUMAnN2.

# Pathway	humann2_Coverage
# Pathway	humann2_Coverage
UNMAPPED	1.0000000000
UNINTEGRATED	1.0000000000
UNINTEGRATED g_Clostridium.s_Clostridium_thermocellum	1.0000000000
UNINTEGRATED g_Coprothermobacter.s_Coprothermobacter_proteolyticus	1.0000000000
UNINTEGRATED g_Methanothermobacter.s_Methanothermobacter_thermautotrophicus	1.0000000000
PWY-6305: putrescine biosynthesis IV	1.0000000000
PWY-6305: putrescine biosynthesis IV g_Clostridium.s_Clostridium_thermocellum	1.0000000000
PWY-7219: adenosine ribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis	1.0000000000
PWY-7219: adenosine ribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis g_Clostridium.s_Clostridium_thermocellum	0.9999999754
PWY-7219: adenosine ribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis g_Coprothermobacter.s_Coprothermobacter_proteolyticus	0.9991738390

Supplementary figure S2c: HUMAnN2 Pathway Coverage: First 10 rows of the pathway coverage results from HUMAnN2.

# Gene Family	humann2_Abundance -RPKs
UNMAPPED	109359
UniRef50_P62593: Beta-lactamase TEM	51842.43044
UniRef50_P62593: Beta-lactamase TEM g__Clostridium.s__ Clostridium_thermocellum	51842.43044
UniRef50_R5FV61	46966.29231
UniRef50_R5FV61 g__Clostridium.s__ Clostridium_thermocellum	46966.29231

Supplementary figure S3: Uniref50 Gene Family output with abundance - Schematic of the workflow including the UniRef results for gene family abundance using the HUMAnN2 tool and further normalization. Shown here are the first 5 rows of the UniRef gene family abundances.

Supplementary figure S4: Conversion of Uniref 50 values to GO terms: Schematic of the workflow assigning Gene Ontology terms (GO terms) to the UniRef gene families. The gene families are sorted into three GO term groups, molecular function, biological process, and cellular component. Given is the first 5 rows of the three Slim GO outputs.